

WAYS OF FAMILY BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT IN THE MODERNIZATION OF THE ECONOMY

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Abstract: the article reveals the role of family entrepreneurship in the development of society. The role in improving the well-being of the family, the level and quality of life through family entrepreneurship, which is one of the most pressing issues today, the role of family members in employment, increasing tax revenues to the budget, the importance of the population in creating many new jobs based on the principle of reducing poverty and improving the well-being of the population.

Keywords: family, family entrepreneurship, well-being, quality of life, standard of living, self-employment, family economy, production, service.

The formation of the digital economy in the conditions of economic modernization, diversification and introduction of innovative factors has led to a radical change in the content of family income and related circumstances. These changes are manifested in the following: a new economic category has entered our economic and social life - the category of the value of labor power; a place where labor is sold based on supply and demand - the labor market; absolute and relative unemployment is arising due to changes in supply and demand for labor force; family members, residents are gradually moving to the principle of providing themselves with work based on the development of entrepreneurship; new sources of family income have appeared - income from property use and business activities; income from the use of property used to consist only of rent, but now, such types of income as dividends, interest, and investment income have entered.

These situations, while ensuring a certain level of stability of the society, also cause some problems. At the root of these problems is the stratification of family incomes, unemployment and, as a result, the problem of the emergence of low-income, poor families. The main way to solve these problems, in our opinion, is to inculcate the need to increase the social activity of the population, to move to the principle of providing self-employment and other necessary benefits, and secondly, every It consists in introducing the mechanism of financial interest in what kind of activity, developing new methods of stimulation. However, in order to ensure the legal foundations of these activities, it is necessary to resolve them at the level of the government and the legislative chamber of the Oliy Majlis.

Currently, it is necessary to develop ways to increase the efficiency of the family's invested funds. These include: extension of the project period; increase (decrease) the dividend rate of the project; it is possible to include things like increasing cash flow. But even these issues have not been sufficiently studied in accordance with the family economy.

Even in the period of transition to the digital economy, inflationary processes are still maintained. Taking this into account, it will be necessary to develop methodological aspects of the assessment and analysis of family property and income in inflationary conditions. Using the nominal and real rates of family income, the total rate of its income from investment is determined. This made it possible to determine the value of the family investment taking into account the inflation after one year and determine its impact on the well-being of the family.

There is a noticeable lack of information on the study of the family economy and its impact on well-being. Because the research conducted by the State Statistics Committee does not fully solve this problem. Because of this, it can be implemented and collected only with the help of sociological research. For this, it is appropriate to develop questionnaires. In our opinion, the following indicators should be included in the questionnaire. The survey can consist of three

parts:

1. General indicators about the family.
2. Structure of family income.
3. Structure of family expenses.

Several indicators are expressed in each part. In our opinion, the data collected on these indicators is a sufficient basis for drawing scientific conclusions. Because, based on these indicators, family incomes and expenses can be classified by the total number of families, the number of working people, and the percentage of non-working people. Several new relative indicators can also be determined from these data. All this serves as a basis for drawing appropriate conclusions and making management decisions.

If our recommendations on collecting data on family incomes and expenses are put into practice, we think that it will be possible to make appropriate management decisions to increase the incomes and optimize the expenses of the families of our country. These indicators are very important in the digital economy. Because, in order to ensure the well-being of every family, it is necessary to take into account their capabilities. This is done using information and communication technologies.

The formation of the digital economy requires a family entrepreneur to have great knowledge and intelligence not only in terms of entrepreneurship, but also in conducting economic affairs. A comprehensive economic knowledge of an entrepreneur brings more income to the household income, and most importantly, it increases the property. More importantly, the size of the property increases by using the property. This is the basis for the enrichment and strengthening of the economic power of the family economy, the entire population, and the state.

At this point, it is necessary to say some thoughts about family business. Because the concepts of family welfare and family business are considered the same concepts in most cases. In this regard, we would like to share our views

without dwelling on the theoretical analysis of the opinions in the economic literature. Based on the concept of entrepreneurship, family business should be evaluated as a profit-generating activity. If it is based on this theory, it is appropriate to define it as follows. Family business is understood as a set of all salable activities related to production, service and work performance that bring income (profit) to the family while owning a certain property. It does not matter whose property it is based on, it is considered only from the point of view of bringing income (profit) to the family.

The importance of this process is not limited to the considered issues. Running a family or household, engaging in family business not only ensures the well-being of the family, but also provides employment for the population in exchange for opening new jobs, and enriches the state for the taxes collected from them. is achieved. Products produced in family farms not only satisfy their own needs, but also fill the country's market with products (works, services). Most importantly, its social and spiritual importance is also incomparable, because it frees the masses from the mentality of tyranny, instills initiative and aspiration. Ultimately, this will increase the activity of society and the masses, accelerate the process of formation of democratic principles of the digital economy, and lead to the reduction of poverty. In short, family entrepreneurship will lead to the improvement of the welfare of the population, the level of living and the quality of our country, as well as the improvement of important factors such as the reduction of the unemployed. Their relationship is shown in the picture below.

As can be seen from the picture, the place and role of family business in the society is very big. The important thing is that family members engaged in family entrepreneurship will be free from being hired and dependent on others, and will have the opportunity to work at their own will. This, in turn, leads to the improvement of everyone. Through the development of family entrepreneurship, first of all, it creates an opportunity to increase the well-being, standard and

quality of life of the family. Because families engaged in family business acquire certain knowledge in this field, desire for life is formed, and family members are saved from the scourge of idleness. All of these bring a certain amount of material wealth to the family and ensure its well-being, as well as the intellectual potential of family members, thereby increasing the quality of human capital and their responsibilities to society.

Secondly, employment of family members is ensured. If the family is engaged in production, they also provide services such as selling and storing the produced products themselves. In this case, he has to learn not only the secrets of production, but also marketing and management. The intellectual potential of Dkmak family members increases involuntarily.

Thirdly, tax revenue for the state will increase. Each family engaged in business pays a certain amount of tax from its income (profit). With this, poor families become dependent on the state, and instead of waiting for help from it, they fill the state budget with entrepreneurship.

Fourthly, due to the development of family entrepreneurship, the poverty level of the population will decrease. First of all, families engaged in entrepreneurship will have the opportunity to provide themselves with material goods to a certain extent. At the same time, in exchange for expanding the scope of work, he will have the opportunity to provide employment to the people around him. In this way, it creates opportunities to save the population from poverty. There are several examples of this today.

Fifth, many new jobs will be created based on the principle of self-employment of the population. If there are unemployed family members, they will not have a temporary opportunity to work in government offices. Because all states are busy. Similarly, entrepreneurs will work with the respective states until they create new jobs. An unemployed person will remain unemployed if they wait for a job vacancy. In such conditions, great opportunities were created for self-

employment in our country.

We raised the issue of creating a self-employed group from such a population.

Now in Uzbekistan, as of January 1, 2023, 63.90 million. people are living there. The average number of family members in our country is 5.1 people. In that case, according to our calculations, the number of families in our republic is more than 6.4 million. If at least one entrepreneur grows up from each family, 6.6 million more people will be created in our country. additional jobs will be created. This is one of the important factors that ensure the abundance of the consumer market of our country. If every entrepreneur brings an average profit of 10,000.0 thousand soums to his family in one year, this means 66,000.0 million soums for the welfare of the family. soum will bring additional benefits. On average, 30 percent of them go to the state (local) budget as taxes and other payments, and another 19,800.0 mln. soum generates additional income.

It is worth noting that the ultimate goal of the reforms implemented in our country is to create decent living conditions for our people and every family. This is certainly a difficult and responsible task. It is not enough to implement only practical measures to achieve this goal. It requires in-depth research in this field and the development of scientifically based recommendations to ensure the well-being of each family. However, the modernization of the economy, the introduction of diversification and innovative factors, the formation of the digital economy require a new approach to this problem. Due to this, at the moment, great attention is being paid to the economic problem of the family economy. This field was included in the science of economic theory and it is now considered as a subject of microeconomics. Thus, we can see that the transformation of the family economy into a subject of microeconomics is not only economic, but also of great social and spiritual importance, that it can accelerate the formation of the digital economy in the country, the modernization of the economy, the introduction of

diversification and innovative factors, and the modernization of society.

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